

CEDEFOP

European Centre for the Development
of Vocational Training

50
YEARS
SHAPING LEARNING AND
SKILLS FOR EUROPE

Cedefop's European Vocational Teacher survey (EVTS)

Irene Psifidou ([0000-0002-5728-7730](tel:0000-0002-5728-7730))

*Cedefop expert, VET for Youth - Teachers and
Trainers Team Facilitator*

ETUCE Strategic discussion:

The role of education trade unions in supporting VET teachers

22 September 2025 online

Impact of global VET teacher crisis

- Teacher burnout – teachers' well-being at risk
- A profession with low attractiveness to young people
- Those who become VET teachers: teaching was not their first career choice
- Novice teachers more likely to be looking for another job
- Dramatic VET teacher shortages

Cedefop supporting VET teachers & trainers through evidence

Research paper

Teachers and trainers in a changing world

Building up competences for inclusive, green and digitalised vocational education and training (VET)
Synthesis report

Persisting challenges and data gaps

Weak link to careers

- CPD rarely tied to salary supplement or career progression

Barriers to access

- Lack of funding
- Conflicts with teachers' work schedules

Limited involvement

- Teachers not engaged in co-design of CPD

Insufficient needs analysis

- For teachers: in most EU MS but sporadic, mainly at regional or local levels
- For trainers: only in 10 EU countries

Rigid entry requirements

- Limited validation of prior on the job / informal learning

Emerging hybrid teachers / trainers model

- Not yet formalised in most countries

Lack of impact evaluation

- No systematic assessment of CPD effectiveness

Cedefop furnishing new evidence

- Advocate for the need to collect:
 - comparable data on **teachers' CPD provision and demand** across Europe
 - comparable evidence on CPD's **effectiveness, drivers and barriers**
- Design the first European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS) to collect the views of 14 000 teachers in initial VET

50 YEARS
European Centre
for the Development
of Vocational Training

**The European Vocational
Teacher Survey
2025-2026**

Teacher shortage - what needs to
change?

EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL
TEACHER SURVEY

50 YEARS
European Centre
for the Development
of Vocational Training

**The European Vocational
Teacher Survey
2025-2026**

Wellbeing in schools - How can we
support it?

EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL
TEACHER SURVEY

50 YEARS
European Centre
for the Development
of Vocational Training

**The European Vocational
Teacher Survey
2025-2026**

Career development for teachers -
how can we do better?

EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL
TEACHER SURVEY

50 YEARS
European Centre
for the Development
of Vocational Training

**The European Vocational
Teacher Survey
2025-2026**

Resources for teachers and students -
where do we fall short?

EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL
TEACHER SURVEY

EVTS objectives

<https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/en/projects/vocational-teacher-survey>

Setting up the EVTS stakeholder group in close collaboration with ETUCE

Scientific leader

Supported by international research team

National VET experts' network

Tripartite EVTS stakeholders' Group
Country representatives & EU social partners (ETUCE, EFEE)

The screenshot shows a calendar titled 'Events' with three entries for EVTS stakeholder group meetings. Each entry includes the event name, date, time, and a virtual event link. The entries are:

- 3rd EVTS Stakeholder group meeting**
DATE: 05 February 2025
TIME: 09:00-12:00 (CET)
VIRTUAL: [meet](#)
#EVTS
- 2nd EVTS Stakeholder group meeting**
DATE: 27 September 2024
TIME: 09:00-12:00 (CET)
VIRTUAL: [meet](#)
#EVTS
- 1st EVTS Stakeholder group meeting**
DATE: 13 May 2024
VIRTUAL: [meet](#)
#EVTS

Boosting collaborative leadership to design and implement EVTS

- Design survey **questionnaire**
- Define **sampling strategy** for a representative survey in initial VET
- Get **endorsement letters** from ministries
- Co-design **incentives strategy** and survey campaign
- **Disseminate findings** at EU and national levels
- **Co-shape** evidence-based **policies**

Join us in its official launch

 | **CEDEFOP** | European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training

SHAPING LEARNING AND SKILLS FOR EUROPE **50** YEARS

Fourth Policy learning forum
Launching the European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS)

25-26 September 2025
Hybrid event

#VETTeachersTrainers
#VETtoolkit #EVTS

[25 September](#)

[26 September](#)

Thank you

www.cedefop.europa.eu

Follow us on social media

© Cedefop, 2025

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18507301](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18507301)

Irene Psifidou

Expert in VET for youth – teachers and trainers

rena.psifidou@cedefop.europa.eu

+30 2310 490 149 ORCID: [0000-0002-5728-7730](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5728-7730)

CEDEFOP

European Centre
for the Development
of Vocational Training